

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABILITY PRACTICES IN FINANCE,
MANAGEMENT, AND ENTREPRENEURIAL STUDIES**

Volume-4, Issue-1, February, 2026

ISSN (Online): 1595-6253

<https://ijois.com/index.php/ijspfmes/index>

A Peer Reviewed (Refereed) International Journal

Article InformationReceived: 29th Dec., 2025Accepted: 20th Jan., 2026Published: 16th Feb., 2026**LEADERSHIP STYLES AND ORGANISATIONAL
CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR OF FOOD AND BEVERAGES
FIRMS IN RIVERS STATE****Dr. Horsfall, Sunday**Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Administration and Management, Rivers State
University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Nigeria**Email:** Sunday.horsfall@ust.edu.ng**D.O.I:** 10.5281/zenodo.18745646**ABSTRACT**

Investigation was on the relationship of leadership styles on organizational citizenship behaviours. The sample consisted of 220 workers of both genders (30.9% men and 69.1% women) of some selected food and beverages firms in Rivers State who completed a questionnaire that included the variables of interest in this study who answered the Multifactorial Leadership Scale and the Organizational Citizenship Behaviours Scale. The Spearman Rank Correlation showed that leadership styles and organizational Citizenship Behaviour are the predictor and criterion variables. The transformational and transactional leadership style positively predicted the Organizational Citizenship Behaviour measures associated to the creation of a more conducive work environment such as altruism or cooperation among colleagues. Transformational leadership style showed greater predictive power on Organizational Citizenship Behaviours than transactional and laissez-faire leadership. It was concluded that transformational leaders are more capable to lead their subordinates in order to take actions that go beyond their prescribed roles.

Keywords: *Leadership styles, Organizational Citizenship Behaviour, Laissez faire, Transactional, and Transformational leadership*

INTRODUCTION

Many firms are striving for sustainability and growth; and the same time putting their utmost efforts to increase their return on investment and performance in the long run. Human capital managers and employees are the two most important determinants of an organization who activate the non-human resources in the operations of an organization. However, leadership is the pivotal tool to keep the employees motivated and utilizing the scarce resources at optimum. The word leadership is considered as a key word in developing countries and referring to an individual who have a capacity to develop a vision and able to transform it into a mission, by following an acceptable and lay down strategy. The influence of that individual, considered as leader, is of

significance level that can influence the socio-economic factors in particular and the society as a whole, and influence the employee behaviour in an organization to achieve the set goals in organization. Leaders are considered as change agents in the society and in organizations, they can produce the best output by managing scarce resources.

Leadership is an important function of management which helps to maximize efficiency and to achieve organizational goals. The word leadership has been described in terms of the position, personality, responsibility, influence process; instrument to achieve a goal, behaviours (Limsila & Ogunlana, 2007). Most definitions have a common theme of directing a group towards a goal. Therefore, the leadership can be broadly defined as the relationship between an individual and a group built around some common interest wherein the group behaves in a manner directed or determined by the leader (Shastri, Shashi Mishra & Sinha, 2010). Leaders can influence the behaviour of their followers through the use of different styles, or approaches, to managing others. For the past three decades, a pair of predominant leadership styles (transactional and transformational leadership) has received a significant amount of attention. Moreover, an effective leader influences follower in a desired manner to achieve desired goals. Different leadership styles may affect organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB), effectiveness and performance. Some people are born to be leaders, but some people are made into leaders.

Leadership therefore is defined as the ability to influence the motivation or competence of other individuals in a group (Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly, 1991). Finding the right people who will be good leaders is important since effective leadership provides more benefits to an organization than any other human factor (Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly, 1991). Perhaps, equally important is identifying and understanding the underlying mechanics that allow the right people to be good leaders.

Leadership, as the definition implies, have their most direct and greatest effect on their followers. Hence, it stands to reason that, in the workplace, what partially makes for a good leader is the ability to effectively motivate followers to engage in behaviours known to have positive outcomes for the organization. The particular interest to this study, are leaders who influence the behaviours of their followers towards achieving organisational goals. However, it is not enough to solely examine the direct relationship between the two. Such a relationship is already well documented, so it now becomes relevant to learn how leaders influence follower OCBs. Indeed, it has been suggested that it is necessary to place more effort on identifying the processes by which leadership influences followers (Bass, 1998; Yukl, 1999) because this is not done much in a systematic way (Avolio, Zhu, Koh, & Bhatia, 2004). In fact, it is advocated that organizations may be the most important social category for individuals (Hogg & Terry, 2000).

This seminar will aid in the understanding of how leadership styles and OCB can increase effectiveness, performance, potentials and success of employees and as well the organisation.

Statement of the Problem

Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is an important variable to understand the behaviour of workers in the organization and affects employees' attitudes towards work such as intention to stay, rate absenteeism, job satisfaction and work turnover rate. Organizationally committed employees have high motivation rates and better job performance. One of the important variables to strengthen organizational citizen or commitment is the existence of a leadership style that motivates employees and makes them feel the importance of the leader presence and work with him. Here in Rivers State, food and beverages firms face many challenges such as globalization, rapid change and slow economic growth, which requires from their leaders to use leadership styles that believe in change and administrative innovation in the face of competition and market

conditions, making them the most dynamic and innovative source of competitive advantage. Accordingly, the research problem in its general framework is related to a weak understanding of the relationship between leadership styles and organizational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The prime objective/aim of this study is to identify the relationship between leadership styles and organizational citizenship behaviour; while the Objectives include:

- i. To ascertain the relationship between leadership styles and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State
- ii. To determine the relationship between Transformational leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.
- iii. To ascertain the relationship between Transactional leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.
- iv. To examine the relationship between Laissez Faire leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

Research Questions

Based on the preceding Research Objective, the following research questions will be formulated.

- i. What is the Relationship between leadership styles and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State?
- ii. What is the Relationship between Transformational leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State?
- iii. What is the Relationship between Transactional leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State?
- iv. What is the Relationship between Laissez Faire leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State?

Statement of Hypotheses

The proposed research work will be guided by the following hypotheses stated in their null form:
H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Leadership styles and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Transformational leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between Transactional leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between Laissez Faire leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State

Significance of the Study

The study seeks to achieve a main aim, which is related to exploring the effect of leadership style on organizational citizenship behaviour. Based on that main aim, this study aims at:

- identifying a level of leadership styles and the level of organizational citizenship behaviour of employees of food and beverages companies in Rivers State.
- identifying impact of leadership styles on organizational citizenship behaviour of employees of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

The Study importance is that it linked a set of variables that weren't linked by previous studies. It combined leadership styles and organizational citizenship behaviour in one study model.

The results of this study will benefit food and beverages firms in Rivers state to improve performance and promote it by adopting an effective leadership style and increasing employee organizational commitment, performance, profitability, efficiency and effectiveness. The results of this study are expected to benefit decision makers in clarifying the effect of leadership styles on organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB).

Conceptual Frame Work

Figure 1. Conceptual frame work of leadership styles and organisational citizenship behaviour.

Source (Adapted): Bass and Avolio (1994); Organ (1988).

The Dimensions which represents the independent variables (Leadership Styles) were adapted in line with the work of Bass and Avolio (1994) while the measures representing the dependent variables (Organizational Citizenship Behaviour) are adapted in line with the work of Organ (1998)

Review of Literature

There exist multiple theories and models of leadership. Some are trait theories in which certain characteristics associated with leadership are identified. There are also personal-behavioural theories that focus on the personal and behavioural characteristics of leaders, and situational theories that involve a best fit between leader and subordinate behaviour and the situation (Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly, 1991). Throughout the years, the various theories and models have stimulated criticisms, so over time more progressive explanations of leadership have arisen.

The Concept of Leadership Styles

Leadership Styles Leadership is defined as the ability to influence others to get things done. It reflects an influence relationship behaviour between leaders and followers in a particular situation with the common intention to accomplish the organization end results (Stogdill, 1948; Bass, 1981). Generally, leadership researchers suggest that an effective leader should be able to articulate vision, instil trust, belief, loyalty and lead employees' talents directly towards achieving the organizational goals (Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1996; Strange & Mumford, 2002; Levin, 1999; Bennis, 2002; DePree, 2002). There are several well established dichotomy approaches to the classification of leadership styles. Stogdill (1963, 1974) proposes a leadership dichotomy as "consideration leadership" and "structure leadership", likewise Fiedler (1967) suggests "task orientation" versus relationship orientation" and Hersey and Blanchard (1977) recommend "concern for people" and "concern for task". However, this study focused on the transactional and transformational leadership style. Past investigation proposed the dichotomy methods of transactional-transformational leadership may be applicable in the study of phenomenological-based leadership styles (Misumi, 1985; Misumi & Peterson, 1985), in addition to the insight's exploration of leaders-subordinates communication patterns (Penley & Hawkins, 1985) that shape both parties influence behaviours. The following section specifically discussed the transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership styles

Transformational Leadership styles:

Transformational leadership refers to leader transformation process involving individuals, group and organization. It involves creating substantive change in the attitude of employees, moral elevation and organization direction. Kuhnert and Lewis (1987) highlighted that transformational leadership "is made possible when a leader's end values (internal standards) are adopted by followers thereby producing changes in the attitudes, beliefs and goals of followers". Similarly, Bryman (1992) has stated that "transforming leadership entails both leaders and followers raising each other's motivation and sense of purpose. This higher purpose is one in which the aims and aspirations of leaders and followers congeal into one. Both leaders and followers are changed in pursuit of goals which express aspirations in which they can identify themselves". It is no doubt that transformational leadership is of great interest of study due to its popularity and attractiveness of this leadership style found to be consistently associated with superior performance (Barling, Weber & Kelloway, 1996; Bass, Avolio, Jung & Berson, 2003; Dvir, Eden, Avolio & Shamir, 2002; Yammarino & Bass, 1990), increased morale-related outcomes such as self-efficacy (Kirkpartick & Locke, 1996), affective commitment (Barling et al, 1996), intrinsic motivation Charbonneau, Barling & Kelloway, 2001) and trust in the leader (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Moorman & Fetter, 1990)

Transformational leadership style concentrates on the development of followers as well as their needs. Managers with transformational leadership style concentrate on the growth and development of value system of employees, their inspirational level and moralities with the preamble of their abilities. According to Bass, the aim of transformational leadership would be to, transform" people and organizations inside a literal sense - to alter them in the mind and heart enlarge vision, insight and understanding clarify reasons make behaviour congruent with values, concepts and brings about changes which are permanent, self-perpetuating and momentum building. According to Bass and Avolio, transformational leadership happens when leader become wider and uphold the interests of the employees, once they generate awareness and acceptance for the purpose and assignment of the group, so when they blend employees to appear beyond their own self-interest for the good of the group. It also encourages followers to view problems from new perspectives, provide support and encouragement, communicates a vision, and stimulates emotion and identification. Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Moorman, & Fetter, (1990), disclosed that transformational leadership had active influence on individual and organizational outcomes such as employee satisfaction and performance. Higher levels of transformational leadership were associated with higher levels of group potency. Positive relationships have also been consistently reported between individual, group and organizational performance. Typically, these findings have been explained as showing that leader behaviours cause basic values, beliefs and attitudes of followers to align with organizational collective interests (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Moorman & Fetter, 1990).

Transactional Leadership styles:

Transactional leadership relies more on "trades" between the leader and follower by which followers are compensated for meeting specific goals or objective criteria. The transactional leader will first validate the relationship between performance and reward and then exchange it for an appropriate response that encourages subordinates to improve performance. Transactional leadership in organizations plays an exchange role between managers and subordinates. Transactional leadership style is understood to be the exchange of rewards and targets between employees and management. Bass and Avolio explained Transactional leaders motivate subordinates through the use of contingent rewards, corrective actions and rule enforcement. Bass Bernard et al explained that transactional leadership depends on contingent reinforcement, either positive contingent reward or the more negative active or passive forms of management-by-exception. Transactional leaders motivate followers through exchange; for example, accomplishing work in exchange for rewards or preferences. Kahai et al found group efficacy to be higher under the transactional leadership style. According to Burns, transactional leader tends to focus on task completion and employee compliance and these leaders rely quite heavily on organizational rewards and punishments to influence employee performance. Past researchers have studied on transactional leadership as the core component of effective leadership behaviour in organizations prior to the introduction of transformational leadership theory (Bass, 1985; Burns, 1978; House, 1977). Exchange relationship is the key element reflected by the transactional leadership. Transactional leaders demand their subordinates to agree with, accepted or complied with their request if the subordinates hope for rewards and resources or avoidance of punitive action (Burns, 1978; Podsakoff, Todor & Skov, 1982; Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Moorman & Fetter, 1990). This exchange process of leadership style has been linked with contingent reward and punishment behaviour and termed as transactional leader behaviour by Bryman (1992). The typical manager who is a transactional leader tends to identify employees lower level needs by determining the goals that subordinates need to achieve and communicate to them on how successful execution of those tasks will lead to receive of desirable job rewards (Avolio & Bass, 1988; Avolio, Waldman & Yammarino, 1991; Bass, 1985, 1990; Zaleznik, 1983). In fact, this process only helps employees to meet their basic work

Laissez faire Leadership Style.

An avoidant leader may either not intervene in the work affairs of subordinates or may completely avoid responsibilities as a superior and is unlikely to put in effort to build a relationship with them. Laissez-faire style is associated with dissatisfaction, unproductiveness and ineffectiveness (Deluga, 1992).

Laissez faire leadership style is distinct from both Theory X and Theory Y. These leaders adopt hands off approach towards followers. Leaders tend to avoid sense of responsibility, are not qualified enough, lack leadership qualities and abilities to direct and make decisions, can't motivate or influence followers, create communication gaps and lack any kind of leadership attributes (Sahaya, 2012). Laissez faire leader is extremely passive leading to lower self-empowerment of subordinates (Harper, 2012). These leaders do not make any attempt to motivate their subordinates. Hence, this leadership style leads to negative outcomes such as more time in completion of work, frustration among subordinates, difficulty in finding meaning and direction of work etc. (Northouse, 2011).

Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB):

Organisational citizenship behaviours (OCBs) are work-related activities performed by employees; such behaviours increase organisational effectiveness beyond the scope of job from Organ's (1988) classification of the five OCB dimensions, a summary has been provided by Srirang (2009) as follow:

- i. Altruism* refers to helping other members of the organisation in their tasks, e.g., voluntarily helping less skilled or new employees, and assisting co-workers who are overloaded or absent, and sharing work strategies.
- ii. Courtesy* concerns preventing problems deriving from the work relationship, e.g., encouraging other co-workers when they are discouraged about their professional development.
- iii. Sportsmanship* means being tolerant on (avoiding complaining) less than ideal circumstances, e.g., petty grievances, real or imagined offences.
- iv. Civic virtue* involves responsibly participating in the life of the organisation, e.g., attending meetings/functions that are not required but that help the organisation, keeping up with changes in the organisation, taking the initiative to recommend how procedures can be improved.
- v. Conscientiousness* refers to dedication to the job and desire to exceed formal requirements in aspects such as punctuality or conservation of resources, e.g., working long days, voluntarily doing things besides duties, keeping the organisation's rules and never wasting work time.

According to Moorman and Blakely (1995), OCBs are beneficial and desirable from an organisational perspective, but managers have difficulty eliciting their occurrence through contractual arrangements and formal rewards because the behaviours are voluntary. This presents a challenge for managers to better understand and address the potential predictors of OCB that elicit such extra-role behaviours as well as their consequences in organisations. This proliferation of the ways that the OCBs manifest has led authors to reflect on the number and the relevance of the dimensions that should be considered within citizenship behaviours (Organ, Podsakoff, & MacKenzie, 2006). These authors argue that if two forms of manifestation of the OCBs have different antecedents and effects, it is reasonable to state that they are, at least partially, different dimensions. Recently, various investigators have focused on a bi-dimensional approach of the OCBs, based on the consideration of two different receivers of the behaviour (Dovidio, Piliavin, Schroeder, & Penner, 2006; Finkelstein, 2006; Finkelstein & Penner, 2004; Williams &

Anderson, 1991). In this sense, they propose, on one hand, that an organizational citizenship behaviour is directed towards individuals (hereafter, OCBI). On the other hand, the aforementioned types of OCB are directed towards the organization (hereafter, OCBO), because they are preferentially directed to benefit the organization as a whole.

Methodology

This research work adopted the correlation analysis. Correlation tries to study a problem in relationship with the variables in question (Kolharr, 2008). A cross-sectional survey type was adopted because data was collected on the primary source at a specific point in time. The target population consist of all the staff of the six (6) food and beverages firms in Rivers state. The simple size was determined using the Taro Yamene (1967) formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = Simple size

N = Population

e = Margin of error which is usually 5%

Using the sub sample formula by Krejcie and Morgan (1970)

$s = xs/p$ where s is the sub sample size for each firm x is the population of employee or staff of each firm, s is the total sample size and p is the total population of all the employees of the firms

According to Muganda and Muganda (2009) 30% of the total population is considered to be adequate sample size. The simple random sample was used to select respondent from each of the sample firms.

Based on the formula a total of 220 respondents were used. Stratified simple method was used to get the respondent per firm from the target population. Information about the number of staff of the firms was provided by the HR department of each firm. Each department formed the strata and every nth employee was provided with the questionnaire until the sample size was reached. The study used self-administered questionnaire to collect primary data. The questionnaire is divided into three (3) sections. Section A contains background information about the respondent. Section B is on Leadership styles and its dimensions and manifest variables. While the section C is on organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB). The questionnaire on leadership styles was adapted from Bass and Avolio (1996), while that of the Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Checklist was adopted from Fox and Spector (2011). Validity is the ability of the research instrument to measure what it is intended to measure (Sekarom, 2010). To ensure that this research work is valid; thorough literature review was done in order to ensure that the research instrument consist of all research variables. The assistance of some post graduate students and lecturers were sought in the research work.

The reliability of an instrument is the extent or degree of consistency (Muganda and Muganda 1989). To achieve this, the research adopted instrument items from existing literatures. The questionnaire was subjected to statistical testing using the Cronbach alpha with above 0.70 as result proving its reliability coefficient as indicated below.

Measures of variables:

In order to measure leadership styles, an 11-item scale developed by Bass & Avolio (1996) as adapted with dimensions comprising of transformational leadership style which has 7 items with a reported coefficient of .986, transactional leadership style with 2 items with also a reported coefficient of .972 and laissez faire leadership style with 2 items and a coefficient of .980. However, in this study a Cronbach alpha value of .930 was recorded for the three dimensions (Transformational, Transactional and laissez faire leadership styles).

Accordingly, the 20-item scale (or checklist) of organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) developed by Fox and Spector (2011) was adopted at the Cronbach alpha value of .870

Result and Findings

Table 1 Results of Spearman Rank Correlation of dimensions and measures of Leadership styles and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB)

Correlations

			TRANSF ORMATI ONAL LEADERS HIP	TRANSA CTIONAL LEADERS HIP	LAISSSEZ FAIRE	ORGANIS ATIONAL CITIZENS HIP BEHAVIO UR
Spearman's rho	TRANSFORMATI ONAL LEADERSHIP	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	1.000 .000 220	.955** .000 220	-.704** .000 220	.670** .000 220
	TRANSACTIONA L LEADERSHIP	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	.955** .000 220	1.000 .000 220	-.669** .000 220	.638** .000 220
	LAISSSEZ FAIRE	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.704** .000 220	-.669** .000 220	1.000 .000 220	-.950** .000 220
	ORGANISATION AL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	.670** .000 220	.638** .000 220	-.950** .000 220	1.000 .000 220

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.930 ^a	.865	.863	6.025

a. Predictors: (Constant), LAISSSEZ FAIRE, TRANSACTIONAL LEADERSHIP, TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Leadership styles and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

The result reported a strong positive correlation between leadership styles and organizational citizenship behaviour ($\rho = .670$, $n = 220$, $p < 0.01$); thus we reject the null hypothesis (**H₀₁**) to state that there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and organizational citizenship behaviour.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Transformational leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

The result reported a strong positive correlation between transformational leadership style and organizational citizenship behaviour ($\rho = .670$, $n = 220$, $p < 0.01$); thus we reject the null hypothesis (**H₀₂**) to state that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership style and organizational citizenship behaviour.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between Transactional leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State.

The result also showed a strong positive correlation between transactional leadership style and organizational citizenship behaviour.

($\rho = .638$, $n = 220$, $p < 0.01$); this results to the non-acceptance of the stated null hypothesis (**H₀₂**) to state that there is significant relationship between transactional leadership style and organizational citizenship behaviour.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between Laissez Faire leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour of food and beverages firms in Rivers State

More so, the result showed a strong negative correlation between laissez faire leadership style and organizational citizenship behaviour.

($\rho = -.950$, $n = 220$, $p < 0.01$); this results to the non-acceptance of the stated null hypothesis (**H₀₂**) to state that there is significant relationship between laissez faire leadership style and organizational citizenship behaviour.

Summary of Hypotheses

The model summary reports a correlation coefficient value of .930^a for the dimensions of leadership styles (transformational, transactional and laissez faire) indicating that there exists a positive association between the dimensions of leadership and organizational citizenship behaviour of firms studied, the R Square value of .865 (86.5%) represents the coefficient of determination which is the explained variation in organizational citizenship behaviour as accounted for by transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership styles of the firm while the remaining 13.5% of citizenship behaviour is explained by other factors outside leadership style; indicative of the fact that citizenship behaviour stance of firms can be enhanced by the type of leadership style adopted.

Discussion of findings

The general objective in this research was to investigate the relationship and impact of leadership styles (Transformational, Transactional and Laissez faire) on the organizational citizenship behaviours of food and beverages firms in Rivers State. The multiple regression analyses evidenced that the transformational leadership style positively and significantly predicted the organizational citizenship behaviours dimension associated to the creation of a favourable organisational climate and the employee, which partially confirms **Hypothesis 1 and 2**. Thus, it

was verified that, in this sample, the leadership style based on relationship of exchange and reward between leaders and subordinates (Bass, 1990) which was only effective to predict the behaviours associated with the dissemination of a good organizational image in its environment. These results are consistent with different earlier studies (Asgari et al., 2008; Podsakoff et al., 2000; Suliman & Obaidly, 2013; Whittington et al., 2009) that also found the predictive power of transformational and transactional leadership on the OCB.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between leadership styles (Transformation, Transactional and Laissez faire) and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB). According to the research findings, a significant relationship is found between the three leadership styles and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour.

Firms or organisations need to focus on a good and effective leadership styles in its management practices so as to promote and motivate their employees to perform more effective, efficient and committed to the organisation, which result in the high performance of the organizations. This phenomenon requires the proper understanding of the concept of leadership and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour; and its relationship with performance, effectiveness and commitment. A leader can play an active role in developing awareness about Organisational Citizenship Behaviour and mentor the employees to engage in extra role behaviours. The results reveal that a transformational leadership style and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour is of a high quality relationship between leaders and their followers. The research paper provides a good frame work for understanding the relationship between existing leadership paradigms and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour in many years to come.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The validity of strong relationships among these three constructs should be replicated in future with larger sample sizes, different measures and profession. Future studies should be conducted using these contemporary leadership paradigms (Bambale, Shamsudin, & Subramaniam, 2011). Consequently, the study focused on food and beverages firms in Rivers State, a similar study could be conducted or carried out in other industries, sectors and states in Nigeria.

References

- Asgari, A., Silong, A. D., Ahmad, A., & Samah, B. A. (2008). The relationship between leader-member exchange, organizational inflexibility, perceived organizational support, interactional justice and organizational citizenship behaviour. *African Journal of Business Management*, 2(8), 138-145.
- Asgari, A.; Silong, A.D.; Ahmad, A.; Sama, B.A. (2008). The relationship between transformational leadership behaviours, leader-member exchange and organizational citizenship behaviours. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(4): 140-151.
- Avolio, B.J.; Zhu, W.; Koh, W.; Bhatia, P. (2004). Transformational leadership and organizational commitment: mediating role of psychological empowerment and moderating role of structural distance. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 25: 951-968.

- Bambale, A. J. A., Shamsudin, F. M., &Subramaniam, C. (2011).Stimulating organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) research for theory development: Exploration of leadership paradigms.*International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 1(3 Special), 38-59.
- Bambale, A. J. A., Shamsudin, F. M., Chandrakantan, A., &Subramaniam, L. (2011).Stimulating organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) research for theory development: Exploration of leadership paradigms.*International journal of academic research in business and social sciences*, 1, 48.
- Bass, B. M., Avolio, B. J., Jung, D. I. &Berson, Y. (2003).Predicting Unit Performance by AssessingTransformational and Transactional Leadership, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(2).
- Bass, B. M. (1981). *Stogdill's Handbook of Leadership (2nd Ed.)*.New York: Free Press.
- Bass, B. M. (1985), *Leadership and Performance*, Free Press, New York.
- Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1994).Introduction in Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (Eds).*Improving Organizational Effectiveness through Transformational Leadership*,pp. 1-10.
- Bass, B.M. (1990a). *Bass and Stogdill's handbook of leadership: Theory, research, and managerial applications*(3rd ed.). New York: The Free Press.
- Bass, B.M. (1990b). From transactional to transformational leadership: Learning to share the vision. *Organizational Dynamics*, 18: 19-31.
- Bass, B.M. (1998). *Transformational leadership: Industry, Military, and Educational Impact*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Barling, J.; Weber, T.; Kelloway, E.K. (1996). Effects of Transformational Leadership Training on Attitudinal and Financial Outcomes: A Field Experiments. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81(6): 827–832.
- Bennis, W. (2002).*On becoming a leader: The leadership classic updated*. New York, NY: Basic Books.
- Bryman, A. (1996). Leadership in Organizations. In Clegg, S. R., Hardy, C., & Nord, W. R. (Eds), *Handbook of Organizational Studies*. Thousands Oaks, CA:Sage.
- Burns, J.M. (1978). *Leadership*. New York: Harper and Row.
- Charbonneau, D., Barling, J. &Kelloway, E.K. (2001). Transformational leadership and sports performance: The mediating role of intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 1, 1521-1534.
- Deluga, R.J. (1992), *The relationship of leader-member exchange with laissez faire, transactional, transformational leadership in naval environments*, in Clark, K.E., Clark, M.B. and Campbell, D.P. (Eds), *Impact of Leadership*, Centre of Creative Leadership, Greensboro, NC.
- DePree, M. (2002), “Servant-leadership: three things necessary”, in Spears, L. (Ed.), *Focus on Leadership: Servant Leadership for the 21st Century*, Wiley, New York, NY.

- Dovidio, J. F., Piliavin, J. A., Schroeder, D. A., & Penner, L. (2006). The social psychology of prosocial behaviour. Mahwah, NJ, US: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- Dvir, T.; Eden, D.; Avolio, B.; Shamir, B. (2002). Impact of transformational leadership on follower development and performance: a field experiment. *Academy of Management Journal*, 45: 735-744.
- Fiedler, F.E. (1967). *A Theory of Leadership Effectiveness*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Finkelstein, M., & Penner, L. (2004). Predicting organizational citizenship behaviour: Integrating the functional and role identity approaches. *Social Behaviour and Personality: An international journal*, 32, 383-398.
- Gibson, J.L., Ivancevich J.M., and Donnelly J.H., (1991). *Organizational Behaviour, Structure and Process*, New York: Richard D. Irwin, Inc.
- Hersey, P., Blanchard, K. and Johnson, D.E. (2001), *Management of Organizational Behaviour*, 8th ed., Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ
- Hogg, M. A., & Terry, D. J. (2000). Social identity and self-categorization processes in organizational contexts. *Academy of Management Review*, 25, 121-140.
- House, R.J. (1977). *A 1976 theory of charismatic leadership*. In: J.G. Hunt & L.L. Larsons (eds.) *Leadership: The Cutting Edge*. Carbondale, IL: Southern Illinois University Press, 189-207.
- Kahai S. S., Sosik J. J. and Avolio B. J. (1997), Effects of Leadership Style and Problem Structure on Work Group Process and Outcomes in an Electronic Meeting System Environment, *Personnel Psychology*, 1-146.
- Kirkpartick, S.A. & Locke, E.A. (1996). Direct and indirect effects of three core charismatic leadership components on performance and attitudes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81, 36-51.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). *Determining sample size for research activities*. Educational and Psychological Measurement, 30, 607-610.
- Kuhnert, K. W., & Lewis, P. (1987). Transactional and Transformational Leadership: A Constructive/Developmental Analysis. *The Academy of Management Review*, 12, 648-656.
- Levin, S.L. (1999). Development of an instrument to measure organizational trust. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, UMI No. 9920326.
- Limsila, K., & Ogunlana, S. O. (2007). Performance and leadership outcome correlates of leadership style and subordinate commitment. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 15(2), 164-184.
- Misumi, J. (1985). *The Behavioural Science of Leadership*. University of Michigan Press, Ann Arbor.
- Misumi, J. and Peterson, M.F. (1985). The performance-maintenance (PM) theory of leadership: Review of a Japanese research program. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 30, 198-223.
- Moorman, R. H., & Blakely, G. L. (1995). Individualism-collectivism as an individual difference predictor of organizational citizenship behaviour. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 16(2), 127-142.

- Northouse, P. G. (2011). *Introduction to leadership: Concepts and practice*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Organ, D. W. (1988). *Organizational citizenship behaviour: The good soldier syndrome*. USA: D.C. Heath and Company.
- Organ, D. W., Podsakoff, P. M., & MacKenzie, S. B. (2006). *Organizational citizenship behaviour: Its nature, antecedents, and consequences*. USA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Penley, L.E. & Hawkins, B. (1985). Studying interpersonal communication in organizations: A leadership application. *Academy of Pedhazur (1997 Journal)*, 28(2), 309-326.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Moorman, R. H., & Fetter, R. (1990). Transformational leader behaviours and their effects on followers' trust in leader, satisfaction, organizational citizenship behaviours. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 1(2), 107-142.
- Sahaya, N. (2012), A learning organization as a mediator of leadership style and firms' financial performance. *International Journal of Business and Management*, Volume 7(14), 96-113.
- Shastri, R.K.; Shashi Mishra, K.; Sinha, A. (2010). Charismatic leadership and organizational commitment: An Indian perspective. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(10): 1946-1953.
- Stogdill, R.M. (1948). Personal factors associated with leadership: A survey of the literature. *Journal of Psychology*, 25, 35-71.
- Stogdill, R.M. (1963). *Manual for the Leader Behaviour Description Questionnaire – From XI. Bureau of Business Research*. Ohio State University, Columbus, OH.
- Stogdill, R.M. (1974). *Handbook of Leadership: A Survey of Theory and Research*. Free Press, New York.
- Strange, J.M. & Mumford, M.D. (2002). The origins of vision: charismatic versus ideological leadership. *Leadership Quarterly*, pp. 343-77.
- Suliman, A., & Obaidly, H. A. (2013). Leadership and organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) in the financial service sector: The case of the UAE. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 115-134.
- Williams, L. J. & Anderson, S. E. (1991). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment as predictors of organizational citizenship and in-role behaviour. *Journal of Management*, pp. 601-617.
- Yammarino, F.J. & Bass, B.M. (1990). Long term forecasting of transformational leadership and its effects among naval officers: Some preliminary findings. In K.E. Clark and M.B. Clark (Eds.), *In Measures of Leadership*, pp.151-169. Greensboro, NC: Center for Creative Leadership.
- Yukl, G. A. (1999). *Leadership in organizations*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Yukl, G. (2002). *Leadership in organizations* (5th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Zaleznik, A. (1983). The leadership gap. *Washington Quarterly*, 6(1), 32-39.